

AN INVESTIGATION OF THE DRIVERS OF AGRICULTURAL SECTOR OUTPUT IN NIGERIA

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<p>Keywords: <i>Agricultural output, Climate change, industrialization and ARDL</i></p>	<p>Abstract: <i>This study examined the impact of manufacturing value added as proxy for industrialization, net migration as proxy for rural-urban migration, carbon dioxide emission as proxy for climate change, agricultural capital expenditure and agricultural recurrent expenditure all as independent variables on agricultural output as dependent variable. The study used the ARDL estimation technique and its Bounds test on data covering the period of 1981 to 2018. The Bounds test revealed the existence of a long-run relationship among the variables and all the independent variables have the correct sign but turned out statistically insignificant. The lack of proper implementation of agricultural capital and recurrent expenditures is pointed to in this study as a reason for their insignificant impact. The short-run results revealed that the second period lag of carbon dioxide emission has a statistically significant impact on agricultural output pointing to the negative impact of climate change on the dependent variable. The short-run results further revealed that the current value and the second period lag of agricultural capital expenditure have a positive statistically significant impact on the dependent variable prompting the recommendation that government should provide more capital equipment for mechanized agriculture and should earmark policies to ensure the sustainability of agricultural infrastructure.</i></p>
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1. INTRODUCTION

For centuries now, food, clothing and shelter have always been considered basic needs of humans but food clearly comes first. Without a doubt, it can be argued that in the worst of situations, humans can do without clothing and

shelter but certainly not food. It is therefore safe to assert that agriculture as the primary source of food is very crucial for the wellbeing of individuals and as such cannot be treated with levity by both governments and individuals. Agriculture refers to the production of various

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crops and livestock as well as forestry and aquaculture for both food and non-food products. It is not only a source of food but also a major source of income for governments and individuals (Mbah, Ezeano and Agada, 2016). In Nigeria, agriculture constitutes a major sector of the economy with a contribution of some 23 percent to real gross domestic product (RGDP) and a share of about 51 percent in total employment (Il Jung, 2023). However, a worrisome reality is that food import ratio remains high when compared to global averages and apart from the early 1970s, food imports have consistently remained higher than food exports. Similarly, the consumption per capita of

key staples remains low compared to world averages. This situation is ironic when considered side by side with the vast array of arable land, the huge vibrant youth population and the enormous budgetary allocation to the agricultural sector annually in Nigeria. Clearly, Nigeria is not achieving even close to her full agricultural potentials despite several efforts made by successive governments in the country. From the era of Operation Feed the Nation (OFN) by the Obasanjo administration of the 1970s to more recent efforts such as the Agricultural Transformation

Fig 1: Food import/export figures in Nigeria

Source: Data Extracted from WDI (2021)

Agenda (ATA) of 2013, similar problems such as yield gaps, inadequate storage facilities, lack of finance for agriculture, poor transportation

network from farms to cities, inadequate agriculture education and general lack of incentives to go into agriculture have continued

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to persist and hamper the growth of the agricultural sector. In recent times, however, and without prejudice to the issue of government expenditure on agriculture which will also be discussed in this work, the triplicate issues of rural-urban migration, industrialization and climate change as they impact on agricultural output seems to have taken the front burner.

Generally, rural-urban migration is the movement of people from rural areas to urban areas whether permanently or temporarily (Igene, Onymekonwu and Ehiwario 2023). While different scholars have pointed to both positive and negative effects of rural-urban migration (Dazhuan and Zhihua 2019, Goldsmith and Kisan, 2004), the negative effect it has on agriculture seem more prominent. Since agriculture in most rural areas in Nigeria is typically labor-intensive in nature, the migration of young people from rural areas in search of greener pastures in urban areas is particularly worrisome as it clearly creates a huge deficit of labor for agriculture in rural areas. Sorenson (2004) points to wealth disparity between rural and urban areas in favor of urban areas as a major reason for movement to urban areas while Ajaero and Mozie (2011) echo similar thought by asserting that rural-urban migration is simply a survival strategy utilized by rural dwellers that have no means of livelihood. However, rural-urban migration is not a standalone problem as it is clearly linked to industrialization. This is because the growth of industries in cities continues to attract the youth in rural population

who believe that they can quickly make life better for themselves by engaging with big industries in urban areas.

Industrialization, which generally means the movement of an economy from only primary agriculture to an economy that manufactures goods, has been identified by scholars to possibly have both positive and negative effects on agriculture (Holkar et al, 2018). Without a doubt, industrialization provides the much-needed tools for mechanized farming which is a *sin qua non* for better agricultural output. By so doing, it can help in generating foreign exchange for a country as greater agricultural output can be huge exports for countries. However, the benefits of industrialization can only be true if it is well managed. But the stark reality on ground in many developing countries like Nigeria seems to suggest otherwise. In fact, the negative effects of industrialization on agriculture generally can be summed up into three. First, it leads to loss of valuable agricultural land as industries encroach into these lands for their setup and activities. To this end, Lu et al (2011) opines that industrialization not only shrinks the forest area but also results in significant changes in the composition of arable land. Second, it leads to loss of agricultural manpower as many youths engaged or capable of being engaged in agriculture now see the industries as a shortcut to wealth {Deepak, Sushil and Rahul, 2020}. Third, the production activities of industries even without physically encroaching into land for agriculture or taking manpower from agriculture

have the capacity of negatively affecting agricultural activities and yield. To this end, Liu et al (2014) stresses that the use of pesticides, chemical fertilizers and sewage irrigation all have the capability of disrupting the natural ecosystem as well as polluting the soil and environment. Similarly, Sethy and Ghosh (2013) contend that industrial wastes have huge concentration of heavy metals which degrades the chemical, biological and physical properties of both plants and animals. But then, just as rural-urban migration is linked to industrialization, the later is also linked to yet another problem that affects agriculture, namely climate change.

Basically, climate change points to long-term weather and temperature variations. Such variations can be naturally caused by factors such as large volcanic eruptions or changes in the sun's activity but more recently caused by human activities. Climate change caused by human activities has been the major cause of worry because of its pervasiveness and the increasing threat it poses the world over. Ayinde, Muchie and Olatunji (2011) emphasizes that the effect of climate change on agriculture is not just limited to crop production but also weighs heavily on livestock production and the entire agriculture sector value chain. Fasona and Omojola (2005) as well as Obioha (2008) point to the devastating effect that long-term reduction in the amount of rainfall has on both flora and fauna resources and the amount of surface water on land in both the North and South of Nigeria.

Keyamo (2025) also decries the 2012, 2018 and 2022 huge floods in Nigeria as possible key outcomes of climate change and this certainly has huge disruptive impact on agricultural activities. With respect to livestock production, swings in wind speed, temperature and humidity can affect not only the growth of animals but also the reproduction and milk production. The quality and quantity of feed stuffs necessary for livestock health and survival can also be affected by climate change.

The trend of government expenditure on the agricultural sector in Nigeria has been worrisome over the years. While it may look good in nominal terms, it portrays a rather gloomy picture when considered as a percentage of total government annual budget. Jimmy and Guluwa (2021) report that in the period of 1980 to 2011, government capital expenditure on agriculture as a percentage of total government budget was generally below ten percent as it only rose above ten percent during years of government special agricultural intervention programs. The outlook of agricultural recurrent expenditure has not been impressive also. For instance, in 2009, government recurrent expenditure on agriculture stood at 22.4 billion naira in contrast to total government recurrent expenditure of 2.13 trillion naira. Agriculture recurrent expenditure rose to 28.2 billion naira and 41.2 billion naira in 2010 and 2011 respectively. While this figure declined to 33.3 billion naira in 2012, for 2013, 2014, 2015 and 2016; it stood at 39.3

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billion naira, 38.67 billion naira, 40.31 billion naira and 41.28 billion naira respectively.

This work focuses on the quadruple impact of rural-urban migration, industrialization, climate change and agricultural expenditure (both capital and recurrent) on agricultural output in Nigeria in the period of 1981 to 2018. This study is significant because it will create a clearer picture of the effect of these three factors on agricultural output and how to tackle them as Nigeria continues to search for food security and better foreign exchange away from oil production. It is noteworthy that agricultural output is proxied by agric sector GDP while manufacturing sector value added, carbon dioxide (CO₂) emission and net migration are proxies for industrialization, climate change and rural-urban migration respectively.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 Theoretical literature

In economic literature, the complex interactions of different economic phenomenon (such as those in this study) or even the complex interactions of non economic phenomenon with economic phenomenon is best explained by the systems theory. The idea is that economic phenomenon, whether they are sectors, variables or agents do not exist in a vacuum and as such continuously impact themselves back and forth. Devereaux and Wagner (2020) emphasize that social systems such as economic systems present very difficult challenge to control from within because of their endless back and forth interactions. Similarly, White (2005) points out

that economic variables are often impacted by non economic agents that economists cannot ignore in their analysis. Apparently, the complex nexus between rural-urban migration, industrialization, climate change and agricultural expenditure on the one hand vis-à-vis agricultural output on the other hand falls under the purview of the systems theory.

2.2 Empirical literature

2.2.1 Climate change and agriculture

Whether in the field of agriculture or economics, researchers especially in recent times have sought to identify how climate change affects agriculture and food security. In their study bothering on the impact of higher CO₂ emission, declining water resources and higher temperature on agricultural output, Muringui et al (2020) found a strong link between varying climatic conditions and poor performance of crops. They also contend from their findings that drought as a result of climate change has seriously negatively affected fishery especially in areas where fish farming depends on natural water. The same is true of Ayinka (2020) who decried the dwindling water resources in the Lake Chad region of Nigeria as a result of climate change which now limits fish production and supply as well as reduces the income of fishermen. Similarly, Ogbuchi (2020) stressed that the unprecedented 2012 flood in Nigeria led to huge loss of crops and livestock further leading to huge rise in prices of food items.

Using time series data between 1975 and 2010 to investigate both the short term and long term

effects of selected climatic variables such as humidity, temperature and rainfall, Idumah et al (2016) found a potent link between the climatic variables and agricultural production. In the same vein, Ogbo et al (2019) from their findings describe as crisis the effect that extreme climatic conditions have on the agricultural system in Nigeria.

2.2.2 Rural-urban migration and agriculture

Economic literature provides studies having to do with the connectivity between rural urban migration and agricultural productivity. Goldsmith and Kisan (2004) examined the nexus between rural urban migration and agricultural output in Senegal. They established, from their findings, a strong relationship between rural urban migration and the proportion of urban per capita income to rural per capita income. Based on this, they recommended greater investments in agriculture in rural areas as this will boost rural per capita income and thus mitigate against further rural urban migration. Similarly, Rozelle et al (1999) took an x-ray of the linkage between rural urban migration, agricultural production and remittances. They found a negative relationship between rural urban migration and agricultural yields and a positive relationship between remittances and rural urban migration. On the contrary, Taylor and Martin (2001) and Lucas (2003) both argued from their study on remittances, migration and agricultural output that remittances constitute a catalyst for greater rural agricultural yield as these remittances can

bridge the investment gap in the rural agricultural sector. The findings of Mendola (2008) also support the claim that migration brings about remittances which serve as investments in technology in the rural agricultural sector.

2.2.3 Industrialization and agriculture

There is consensus among many scholars of a symbiotic relationship between industrialization and agricultural output (Deepak and Rahul 2020). In other words, industrialization can spur agricultural productivity as much as agricultural productivity can induce greater industrialization. Scholars such as Holkar et al (2018) as well as Saritha and Jangra (2024) point to the enormous positive effects of industrialization on agricultural output such as improved storage and preservation facilities, easy multiplicity of seeds, fast farming processes as a result of mechanized farming just to mention a few. On the flip side, Horrigan et al (2002), Hendrickson and James (2005) as well as Bhateria and Jain (2016) all decry the negative impact of industrialization on agriculture such as soil degradation as a result of industrial effluent, poor health of livestock and fishery as a result of air and water pollution and the loss of agricultural land as a result of industry establishment and expansion.

2.2.4 Government expenditure and agriculture

Vincent and Shadrach (2021) examined the impact of government recurrent expenditure on agricultural productivity and economic growth in Nigeria. using the ARDL estimation technique on

data covering the period of 1980 to 2019, the study found a strong significant relationship between government agricultural recurrent expenditure and economic growth as well as agricultural output. The study thus recommended increased funding of the agricultural sector by government. In addition, it was recommended that government should earmark policies that will encourage deposit money banks to lend more to farmers. Other studies such as Ebere and Osundina (2012), Okezie, Nwosu and Njoku (2013) and Idoko and Jatto (2018) all show similar results of a positive linkage between government expenditure and agricultural productivity. On the contrary, Loto (2011) investigated government spending on agriculture and economic growth and surprisingly found a

negative relationship between the variables in the short-run. On their part, Etian and Chiedza (2022) in their study on the impact of government expenditure on agriculture on selected variables in the value of agricultural production found out that there is no Granger causality from government agricultural spending to agricultural output. Olubokun et al (2016) as well as Edeh, Ogbodo and Onyekwelu (2020) both found a negative link between government recurrent agricultural spending and agricultural output.

3. Methodology

3.1 Data and sources

Time series data are employed in this work. They are drawn from the various sources as indicated in Table 1.

Table 1: Data and their sources

VARIABLE	DESCRIPTION	SOURCE
AGDP	Agricultural Sector Gross Domestic Product in real terms which is the annual output of the agricultural sector after taking into account the effect of inflation. This is proxy for agricultural output calculated in billions of Naira.	Nigeria Bureau of Statistics (NBS).
MVA	Manufacturing Value Added which is the output of the manufacturing sector calculated in billions of Naira as proxy for industrialization.	World Development Indicators (WDI).
NM	Net Migration is the number of immigrants less the number of emigrants in a given place over a given time period; in this case in rural areas in Nigeria as proxy for rural urban migration	Nigeria Bureau of Statistics (NBS).
CO	Carbon dioxide emission which is the release of carbon dioxide into the atmosphere. This is proxy for climate change	World Development Indicators (WDI).
ACEX	Agriculture Capital Expenditure a constant prices which is the total annual capital spending on agriculture by the government	CBN Statistical Bulletin
AREX	Agriculture Recurrent Expenditure a constant prices which is the total annual recurrent spending on agriculture by the government	CBN Statistical Bulletin

3.2 Estimation technique and model specification

Autoregressive Distributed Lag (ARDL) technique is the estimation technique of this work. The ARDL technique is very useful for establishing both short run and long run relationships between variables. Usually, in econometric investigations, the choice of an estimation technique is informed by the results of certain preliminary tests carried out on the data to be used for the investigation. One of such preliminary tests is the Unit Root Test or stationarity test which reveals the order of integration of the variables. Put in simpler language, the Unit Root Test reveals whether the variables diverge from or converge to their mean over time. If they diverge from their mean over time, the variables are said to have a unit root and estimation based on them may not be reliable. On the other hand, if they converge to

$$AGDP = f(MVA, NM, CO, ACEX, AREX) \dots\dots\dots 1$$

When expressed in linearised logarithmic form, equation 1 becomes:

$$LogAGDP = \beta_0 + \beta_1 LogMVA + \beta_2 LogNM + \beta_3 LogCO + \beta_4 LogACEX + \beta_5 LogAREX + U_1 \dots 2$$

While β_0 is the intercept, $\beta_1, \beta_2, \beta_3, \beta_4$ and β_5 are all parameters to be estimated. U_1 is the stochastic term. The a priori expectation is that β_1 and β_2 can have either a positive or negative sign while β_3 is expected to have a negative sign. β_4 and β_5 are expected to have a positive sign. In the event that the variables are not well-behaved, equation 2 is re-specified as follows:

$$\Delta AGDP = \beta_0 + \beta_1 (\Delta MVA_{t-i}) + \beta_2 (\Delta NM_{t-i}) + \beta_3 (\Delta CO_{t-i}) + \beta_4 (\Delta ACEX_{t-i}) + \beta_5 (\Delta AREX_{t-i}) + U_1 \dots 3$$

Where Δ is the difference operator while $t-1$ represents the unknown lags. In the event of cointegration, the Error Correction Model is specified as follows:

$$\Delta AGDP = \beta_0 + \beta_1 (\Delta MVA_{t-i}) + \beta_2 (\Delta NM_{t-i}) + \beta_3 (\Delta CO_{t-i}) + \beta_4 (\Delta ACEX_{t-i}) + \beta_5 (\Delta AREX_{t-i}) + \beta_6 (ECM_{t-i}) + U_1 \dots\dots\dots 4$$

Where β_6 is the speed of adjustment.

their mean over time, they do not have a unit root and are considered stationary and as such appropriate for parametric estimation. Emeka and Aham (2016) stress that the ARDL technique is applicable if the order of integration of the variables is $1(0), 1(1)$ or a combination of both. They however warn that the technique crashes if the order of integration is $1(2)$.

To establish and interpret long run relationship among variables, the ARDL technique uses the Bounds Cointegration Test. Contrary to what is obtainable in the Johansen and Juselius test for cointegration, the ARDL Bounds Test for cointegration helps to identify the cointegrating vectors. In other words, each variable stands as a single long run equation.

Having established the above and with all variables as defined in Table 1, the model is specified as follows:

4. Results and interpretation

4.1 Unit root test

Table 2: Unit Root Test (Augmented Dickey-Fuller Statistic)

VARIABLES	LEVELS	FIRST DIFFERENCE	DECISION
AGDP	-4.519203	-3.369801	1(0)
MVA	-2.904278	-4.475219	1(1)
NM	-3.975083	-4.839041	1(0)
CO	-2.724484	-6.769595	1(1)
ACEX	-1.815123	-6.719808	1(0)
AREX	-4.507194	-8.106426	1(1)

Source: Author's computation from Eviews

It is evident from Table 2 that some of the variables are stationary at levels while others are stationary at first difference paving the way for the use of the Autoregressive Distributed Lag estimation technique as well as its Bounds Test.

4.2 Bounds test

The Bounds test is the tool used in determining whether a long-run relationship exists among variables. It is presented in Table 3.

Table 3: ARDL Bounds test

ARDL Bounds Test

Sample: 5 38

Included observations: 34

Null Hypothesis: No long-run relationships exist

Test Statistic	Value	K
F-statistic	5.529438	5

Critical Value Bounds

Significance	I0 Bound	I1 Bound
10%	2.26	3.35
5%	2.62	3.79
2.5%	2.96	4.18
1%	3.41	4.68

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Source: Author’s computation from Eviews

It is clear in Table 3 that the F-statistic of 5.529438 is greater than the upper bound at the 5% significance level and even all other significance levels. On this basis, it is clear that there is a long run relationship among the variables. Thus, the long run and short run estimates are showcased in Table 4 and Table 5 respectively.

Table 4: Long-run estimates

Long Run Coefficients				
Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
MVA	0.000000	0.000000	0.155068	0.8787
NM	4822.40608	85017.645945	0.961089	0.3508
CO	-0.000029	0.000231	-0.124420	0.9025
ACEX	427.993600	241.552974	1.771842	0.0955
AREX	51.840929	65.639044	0.789788	0.4412
C	4344.08841	117129.135547	-0.253608	0.8030

Source: Author’s computation Eviews

In Table 4, all the variables meet their apriori expectation but turn out to be statistically insignificant. Recall that MVA and NM could have either a positive or negative sign. Both turn out to be positive indicating that they have the potential of stimulating agricultural output. Also, the negative sign of the coefficient of CO indicates that carbon dioxide emission (climate change) has the potential of reducing agricultural output. A gap in proper implementation of both capital and recurrent agricultural expenditure is a possible reason for the insignificant impact of ACEX and AREX on agricultural output. Elem (2016) has stressed that poor implementation of government policies

often negates against achieving expected macroeconomic outcomes.

The short run results in Table 5 indicate that the coefficients of MVA and NM are both positively related to agricultural sector output but are not statistically significant and they have no lagged effect on agricultural output. The current value of CO surprisingly has a positive effect on AGDP but its first and second lags have the expected negative effect on AGDP but only its first lag is statistically significant. This indicates that the negative effect of CO on agricultural output is not instantaneous. Surprisingly again, the third period lag of CO has a statistically significant positive impact on AGDP. This may point to the efficacy of short term measures by government to

curb the impact of climate change on agricultural activities. For instance,

Table 5: Short run estimates

ARDL Cointegrating And Long Run Form
 Dependent Variable: AGDP
 Selected Model: ARDL(2, 0, 0, 4, 3, 3)
 Sample: 1 38
 Included observations: 34

Cointegrating Form				
Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
D(AGDP(-1))	-0.531817	0.279161	-1.905058	0.0749
D(MVA)	0.000000	0.000000	0.145266	0.8863
D(NM)	362.394415	412.322004	0.878911	0.3925
D(CO)	0.000017	0.000014	1.216429	0.2415
D(CO(-1))	-0.000037	0.000015	-2.438556	0.0268
D(CO(-2))	-0.000000	0.000017	-0.013129	0.9897
D(CO(-3))	0.000044	0.000017	2.502743	0.0235
D(ACEX)	15.475337	5.616060	2.755550	0.0141
D(ACEX(-1))	3.156260	5.746535	0.549246	0.5904
D(ACEX(-2))	-19.665986	6.216215	-3.163659	0.0060
D(AREX)	-2.549400	1.862339	-1.368923	0.1899
D(AREX(-1))	-1.556287	1.403398	-1.108942	0.2838
D(AREX(-2))	-2.124953	1.521716	-1.396419	0.1817
CointEq(-1)	-0.075148	0.049827	-1.508186	0.1510

$$\text{Cointeq} = \text{AGDP} - (0.0000 * \text{MVA} + 4822.4061 * \text{NM} - 0.0000 * \text{CO} + 427.9936 * \text{ACEX} + 51.8409 * \text{AREX} - 4344.0884)$$

R-Squared = 0.99, Adjusted R-Squared = 0.99, DW Statistic = 2.04

Source: Author’s computation Eviews

government usually embarks on special interventions after major disasters such as flood or drought. The current value of agricultural capital expenditure (ACEX) has the expected positive impact on AGDP and the impact is statistically significant indicating that

mechanized farming methods have an instantaneous impact on agricultural output. On the other hand, the first period lag of ACEX is positive but statistically insignificant while the second period lag is negative and statistically significant. The relationship of the second period

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lag to AGDP must be an indication of poor maintenance culture of mechanized farming equipment and agricultural infrastructure provided by government such that they become counterproductive after a short period. The current value as well as the first and second period lags of agricultural recurrent expenditure (AREX) are all negative but statistically insignificant. This negative relationship which is clearly odd might just point to the obvious problem of much government funding on agriculture not getting to the intended hands of actual farmers as such funding corruptively find their way into the pockets of individuals who do not use them for agricultural purposes. Finally, the R-Squared as well as the Adjusted R-Squared of 99% shows that the model has a good goodness of fit and the Durbin-Watson (DW) Statistic of 2.04 indicates the model is free from autocorrelation.

5. Conclusion

This study set out to investigate the impact of five determinants of agricultural output namely manufacturing value added (MVA) as proxy for industrialization, net migration (NM) as proxy for rural urban migration, agricultural capital and recurrent expenditures as proxies for government expenditure on agriculture and carbon dioxide emissions (CO) as proxy for climate change on the level of agricultural output in Nigeria. While the ARDL specified model indicated a long run relationship among the variables, all the variables turned out statistically insignificant in the long run even though they

met their expected signs. With respect to ACEX and AREX, the study adduced this insignificant relationship to possible gaps in proper utilization and implementation of agricultural expenditure. In the short run, ACEX has the most potent positive impact on agricultural output clearly implying that a shift from crude labor-intensive agriculture to mechanized agriculture is very crucial to improve agricultural output in Nigeria. On this basis, more government capital expenditure on the agricultural sector is highly recommended and policy measures should be put in place to track these expenditures to ensure they are actually used to provide capital equipment and infrastructure in the agricultural sector.

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